

Peptide-based biosensor for real-time monitoring of protease biomarker activity using multi-parametric surface plasmon resonance spectroscopy

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ABSTRACT:

Matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9) is a key biomarker targeted in biosensing applications due to its involvement not only in maintaining good health but also in triggering various diseases such as cancer. While quantitative detection of MMP-9 is widely performed using bioanalytical detection kits such as enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), faster, label-free and real-time monitoring of MMP-9 activity would lead to improved disease diagnosis with better understanding of its role in underlying disease progression and development of therapeutic strategies. In this work, multi-parametric surface plasmon resonance spectroscopy (MP-SPR) is used to develop a highly sensitive MMP-9 sensor using immobilized synthetic peptides as MMP-9 substrates. Upon binding to MMP-9, the MMP-9 specific peptide is hydrolyzed between two sites of the amino acid sequence (P1 Gly and P1' Met), resulting in a decrease in the SPR signal response. The sensor detects different concentrations of MMP-9 in buffer and cell culture medium (RPMI-1640), indicating that it can be used under physiological conditions. The limit of detection (LOD) for MMP-9 in buffer is 0.34 pM and the linear detection range is between 5 pM and 9 nM, covering the clinically relevant detection range of MMP-9. To our knowledge, this is the first short synthetic peptide-based MP-SPR biosensor for monitoring MMP-9 activity. The sensor is faster than ELISA (minutes vs. hours) and provides real-time detection with access to binding kinetics information. The use of MP-SPR provides information on surface coverage and peptide thickness before and after cleavage, which is unique compared to other detection methods.

Keywords: Peptide-based biosensor; Matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs); Synthetic peptides; Multi-parametric surface plasmon resonance spectroscopy (MP-SPR); Real-time detection; Non-invasive

1. Introduction

The human body is prone to several life-threatening diseases including cancers, neurodegenerative disorders, and inflammatory diseases. Some challenges in treating these diseases are their rapid progression rates (Nisiewicz et al., 2022), weak predictabilities (Kowalczyk et al., 2023), missing highly sensitive detection methods, and the lack of reliable biomarkers for their diagnosis, prognosis, and therapy success (Xiang et al., 2023). Thus, there is an urgent requirement to develop novel, sensitive, and selective diagnostic tools to identify the target biomarkers at its onset.

Among various disease biomarkers, the overexpressed activity levels of proteases like matrix metalloproteinase-9 (MMP-9) are gaining a lot of attention in research and clinical applications due to their strong involvement in triggering and progression of multiple forms of diseases. MMP-9 belongs to a family of zinc-dependent endopeptidases and is a key biomarker in cancer cell progression and metastasis (Kowalczyk et al., 2023; Lee et al., 2009; Nisiewicz et al., 2022), and Alzheimer's disease (Shin et al., 2013), and is used as a peripheral biomarker of neuroinflammation in multiple sclerosis (MS) (Biela et al., 2015). Moreover, MMP-9 is a wound biomarker due to its extremely high level of expression in chronic wounds (Hugo et al., 2023; Kang et al., 2019).

Some of the gold standard methods that are extensively used in MMP-9 detection are enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) (Ding et al., 2021; Shabani et al., 2020), zymography (Młynarczyk et al., 2023; VEČURKOVSKÁ et al., 2023), and fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) assays (Fudala, et al., 2013; Synak et al., 2019). ELISA is based on antibodies. Although ELISA is highly sensitive and specific, its use is restricted due to high material costs and it is suitable for measuring only protease concentration but not enzymatic activity (Palomar et al., 2020). ELISA is laborious (Hugo et al., 2023), expensive, time-consuming (Wang et al., 2024a), and the evaluation of the kinetics of protease activity is difficult (Shoji et al., 2011). Zymography is a gel-based method and has proved to be sensitive to detect active MMP-9 in various samples including tissue sample (VEČURKOVSKÁ et al., 2023). Unlike ELISA, zymography does not require expensive antibody usage (Wilkesman & Kurz, 2017). However, since this method relies on substrate gel electrophoresis, the method can be used only for limited members of MMPs (Jian et al., 2024). Additionally, zymography suffers from limited target specificity, reproducibility issues (VEČURKOVSKÁ et al., 2023), and low sensitivity (Nisiewicz et al., 2022). In contrast, fluorescence-based MMP-9 assays are common tools for determining MMP-9 activity and its affinity to the ligand by measuring the increase in fluorescence after the cleavage of a specific protease substrate. FRET-based MMP-9 assays are inexpensive and time-efficient and present a direct correlation between the enzymatic activity and signal (Goddard & Reymond, 2004). Nevertheless, FRET-based assays require the

presence of suitable donor/acceptor pairs that exhibit overlap of the donor emission spectrum with the acceptor excitation spectrum (Förster, 1948). This, together with poor soluble organic dyes, short fluorescence lifetimes, chemical instability, and weak signals (George et al., 2003) limits its application. In addition, all the above-mentioned biochemical assays are not suitable for in-situ disease diagnosis (Kang et al., 2019). Therefore, there is an increasing need to shift the paradigm of MMP-9 detection methods from traditional assays to biosensors that offer a simple real-time study of MMP-9 in a highly sensitive approach while vastly maintaining time- and cost-effectiveness.

Currently, biosensors based on biorecognition elements such as collagen (Shoji et al., 2011), antibodies (Lee et al., 2009), aptamers (Hugo et al., 2023), and peptides (Shin et al., 2013) are integrated with different types of detection techniques to ensure sensitive detection of MMP-9. Collagen is one of the fundamental constituents of the extracellular matrix (ECM) and accounts for approximately 30% of its total protein content (Wang et al., 2024b). Due to their triple helical confirmation, collagens have high tensile strength and resistant to degradation by several enzymes (Shoji et al., 2011). However, the triple helical structure of collagen can be hydrolyzed by the family of Matrix metalloproteinases (MMPs). Therefore, collagen is a natural substrate to detect MMP-9 activity (Shoji et al., 2011), however, the sensors with collagen as substrate suffer some major challenges. Collagen is susceptible to structural variability and is non-specific for MMP-9. It might bind or interact with other biomolecules on the sensor resulting in interference signals. The use of antibodies to quantify MMP-9 is reported by Lee et al. (Lee et al., 2009). Nevertheless, antibodies can degrade over time and hence are unstable, and can be expensive to use. Compared to antibodies, DNA-aptamers are structurally more stable (Hugo et al., 2023) if the experimental parameters such as the pH of the solution, temperature are properly maintained. If the temperature, pH and ionic strength of the solution are not properly maintained, aptamers are prone to structural instability due to disrupted folding (Hugo et al., 2023; Jakab et al., 2023). Peptides, on the other hand, are simple to handle and have proved to be structurally and chemically very stable if the length and amino acid residues are properly selected. Unlike antibodies, synthetic peptides of variable length and with MMP-9 specific sequences are easy to synthesize, cost-effective to produce in large quantities with longer stability (Palomar et al., 2020). Peptides also reduce non-specific interactions due to their anti-fouling property resulting in reduced false signal contributions. Therefore, among whole proteins, short synthetic peptide stands out as one of the most suitable candidates to study MMP-9. Moreover, peptide-based biosensors are extremely versatile and can be used to investigate other classes of proteases by designing specific peptide sequences (Rai et al., 2024).

Due to their simplicity and structural reliability, peptides are integrated with a wide range of optical and electrochemical detection techniques to study MMP-9. The working principle of the

sensor is dependent on detection in alteration in signal change due to the enzymatic cleavage of peptides functionalized on the sensing platform. Shin et al., used an electroactive MMP-9 specific peptide (labeled with methylene-blue (MB)) to develop an electrochemical biosensor combined with square wave voltammetry (Shin et al., 2013). Despite of the sensor being able to detect MMP-9 released from cells, the sensor showed incomplete signal suppression even at higher concentrations of MMP-9 due to incomplete peptide cleavage and therefore reduced sensor sensitivity. Such a reduction in signal suppression was also reported by Biela et al. (Biela et al., 2015). The degradation of hydrogel films cross-linked with an MMP-9 specific peptide was monitored using electrochemical impedance spectroscopy. Moreover, to obtain a higher sensor performance, an electroactive species ($K [Fe (CN)_6]^{3-/4}$) was employed. The sensor was able to differentiate between MMP-9 and MMP-2 which are structurally very similar enzymes. However, a larger variation in the peptide degradation signal was observed which was due to non-specific adsorption of digested hydrogels on the surface.

In addition to the above discussed detection techniques, we developed a simple peptide-based biosensor to detect MMP-9 using multi-parametric surface plasmon resonance spectroscopy (MP-SPR) (Fig.1). MP-SPR allows real-time control of peptide immobilization at the sensor surface (Rai et al., 2024), followed by real-time characterization of concentration dependent activity of MMP-9. Since this technique does not need any labelling of the substrate or use of electroactive species, the measurement is simple with a rapid detection mechanism and free of any false signals that could result from unwanted interactions of labels and redox species. In addition to enzyme activity, MP-SPR facilitates examination of several other sensor properties such as the surface coverage and layer thickness, and kinetic analysis of biomolecular interactions taking place on the sensing surface (<https://www.bionavis.com/applications/molecular-interactions-drug-development>). The sensor is activity-based in which the signal detection mechanism completely depends on the determination of signal change due to the proteolytic degradation of the target peptide upon exposure to MMP-9. In the literature, the peptide consisting of a P1 Gly, P1' Met cleavage site is a favorable site for MMP-9 (Netzel-Arnett et al., 1991). Therefore, the target peptide used in this study was based on Dnp-Pro-Leu-Gly-Met-Trp-Ser-Arg-NH₂ (MMP-9 $K_M = 7.78 \pm 1.67 \mu M$, $V_{max} = 0.0056 \pm 0.0005 \text{ nm/s}$ $k_{cat} / K_M = 557198 \pm 127529 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Fig. S3 in the supplementary information) with an additional residue for immobilization on the biosensor surface at the C-terminal end. Our detection method is extremely simple and sensitive to detect MMP-9 without applying additional signal amplification strategies.

Fig. 1. Scheme of a) MP-SPR detection setup showing a laser source from which a p-polarized light of a particular wavelength is directed through a prism onto the Au coated sensor surface. The system is in contact with the flow cell. At a particular angle (Θ) of the incident light, the entire incident light is reflected back into a photodetector. This is called total internal reflection region (TIR). With increasing angle (Θ) of the incident light, surface plasmons are excited on Au establishing a plasmonic layer. b) SPR intensity curve displays the angular scan of the surface showing the maximum light reflected at TIR region, slowly diminishing and reaching a SPR peak minima at which surface plasmons are excited. The SPR intensity curve shifts in angle (Θ) when biomolecular interactions are occurring on Au surface. The change in angle against time can be visualized in sensogram. An example of change in intensity curve and sensogram of peptide before and after its interaction with MMP-9 is shown. c) Peptide-based biosensing platform engineered on gold (Au) before and after its exposure to MMP-9.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Reagents

Matrix metalloproteinase MMP-9 (Pre-Activated Human Recombinant) was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Taufkirchen, Germany). Stock solutions of 500 nM MMP-9 were prepared by adding Glycerol and DI water (60:40) and stored at $-80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Phosphate buffered saline (PBS) tablets (1000 ml/tablet) were purchased from Carl Roth GmbH + Co KG (Karlsruhe, Germany). The linker molecule (LA-PEG-Mal) was purchased from Biopharma PEG Scientific Inc. (Biochempeg Scientific, Watertown, MA, USA). The phenol-red free cell culture media RPMI-1640 without serum was bought from Sigma-Aldrich (Taufkirchen, Germany) and was diluted with 10 mM HEPES (Sigma-Aldrich, Taufkirchen, Germany) before the measurements. To calculate the effective thickness of peptide ACD/ChemSketch (freeware) 2021.2.1 was used. For MP-SPR measurements, the buffer was prepared by diluting 1 PBS tablet in 1000 ml of DI water to obtain 1x PBS solution containing 140 mM NaCl, 2.7 mM KCl, 10 mM phosphate,

degassed for 10 min, and finally adjusted to pH 7.4 with 1 M HCl and 1 M NaOH. All reagents and solvents were purchased in analytical grade quality and used without further purification. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Fourier 300 MHz spectrometer. Chemical shifts δ are indicated in parts per million (ppm), with the residual proton peaks of the solvent (DMSO- d_6 from Deutero GmbH) as internal standard. The identities and purities of the final compounds were determined by a combined HPLC/ESI-MS analysis using either an Agilent 1100 series HPLC system with an analytical Agilent Zorbax SB-Aq (4.6 x 150 mm) or a Waters Alliance e2695 HPLC system with an analytical MZ-Aqua Perfect C18 (4.6 x 250 mm, 10 μ m) column coupled to a Waters Acquity QDa single quadrupole detector. Both instruments were used with the mobile phase: MeCN/H₂O + 0.1% HCOOH = 10:90 to 100:0; (flow rate: 0.7 mL/min; t = 10 min) and a column at 40 °C oven temperature. Samples were applied using 5–10 μ L injection with AUC evaluation at 210 nm and 254 nm. Electro spray ionization (ESI-) mass spectra were recorded on an Agilent 1100 series LC/MSD Ion trap spectrometer in the positive ion mode. All tested peptides have a purity \geq 95%. Fourier-transformed ATR-corrected IR spectra were measured on an Avatar 330 single crystal spectrometer from ThermoNicolet. Melting points (uncorrected) were determined using a Schorpp Gerätetechnik MPM-H3 melting point device using semi-open capillaries. Purification of the final compounds was carried out either on a Varian PrepStar system (model 218) with a preparative MZ-Aqua Perfect C₁₈-column (20 x 250 mm, 7 μ m) by MZ-Analysentechnik or on a 1290 // Infinity preparative LC system from the company Agilent with a preparative column from InfinityLab Pursuit XRs C₁₈ (30 x 250 mm, 5 μ m). A gradient method from 10:90 to 100:0 H₂O: ACN (+0.1% HCOOH) was used.

2.2. Choice of Peptides

Different peptides were synthesized for the characterization of the MMP-9 activity (Fig. 2). The detailed procedure of peptide synthesis is provided in the supplementary section S2.

- Peptide I: The amino acid sequence is Dnp-Pro-Leu-Gly-Met-Trp-Ser-Arg-Cys-NH₂ (MW: 1114.27 g / mol). Peptide I was prepared according to the general procedure of SPPS to afford the final product as a yellow solid. Yield: 40 mg, 0.036 mmol, 11%; ESI-MS: m/z calculated for C₄₇H₆₇N₁₅O₁₃S₂ [M+H]⁺ = 1114.46 (100%); found: [M+2H]²⁺ = 558.00. Purity: 95% (HPLC, 254 nm, MeCN/H₂O = 10:90 to 100:0 + 0.1% HCOOH, t_R = 4.82 min).
- Peptide II: The amino acid sequence is Dnp-Pro-Leu-Gly-Met-Trp-Ser-Arg-Gly-Gly-Cys-NH₂ (MW: 1228.37 g / mol). Peptide II was prepared according to the general procedure of SPPS to afford the final product as a yellow solid. Yield: 57 mg, 0.046 mmol, 14%; ESI-MS: m/z calculated for C₅₁H₇₃N₁₇O₁₅S₂ [M+H]⁺ = 1228.50 (100%); found: [M+2H]²⁺ = 615.00. Purity: 95% (HPLC, 254 nm, MeCN/H₂O = 10:90 to 100:0 + 0.1% HCOOH, t_R = 4.72 min).

The target peptides (Peptide I and Peptide II) are almost identical in their amino-acid sequences and consist of an MMP-9 specific cleavage site and a C-terminal Cys residue for immobilization. Peptide II is slightly longer due to an additional Gly-Gly linker.

- Peptide III: The control peptide III with the amino acid sequence Z-Val-Trp-Arg-Cys-NH₂ (MW: 695.84 g / mol) does not contain the MMP-9 cleavage site. Peptide III was prepared according to the general procedure of SPPS to afford the final product as a white solid. Yield: 9 mg, 0.013 mmol, 4%; ESI-MS: m/z calculated for C₃₃H₄₆N₉O₆S [M+H]⁺ = 696.33 (100%); found: [M+H]⁺ = 696.25 (100%). Purity: 99% (HPLC, 254 nm, MeCN/H₂O = 10:90 to 100:0 + 0.1% HCOOH, t_R = 4.50 min).
- Peptide IV: Peptide for FRET activity assay, sequence: Dnp-β-Ala-Pro-Leu-Gly-Met-Trp-Ser-Arg-NH₂ (MW: 1068.47 g/mol). Peptide IV was prepared according to the general procedure of SPPS to afford the final product as a yellow solid. Yield: 46 mg, 0.043 mmol, 13%; ESI-MS: m/z calculated for C₄₇H₆₈N₁₅O₁₃S [M+H]⁺ = 1082.48 (100%); found: [M+2H]²⁺ = 542.00 (100%). Purity: 98% (HPLC, 254 nm, MeCN/H₂O = 10:90 to 100:0 + 0.1% HCOOH, t_R = 4.74 min).

Fig. 2. Structure of peptides used in this work. a) Target peptide I. b) Target peptide II with additional Gly-Gly linker. c) Control peptide III. d) Peptide IV used for FRET activity assay.

2.3. Enzyme activity assay in solution (FRET)

The fluorometric assay was performed with a Tecan Spark 10 M plate reader using Greiner Bio-One black-bottom 96-half-area well plates. The measurements were performed as technical triplicates in a total volume of 50 μ L. Each well contained 48 μ L buffer (150 mM NaCl, 50 mM Tris-HCl pH 7.5, 20 μ M ZnCl₂, 1 mM CaCl₂, 0.05%-Brij), 1 μ L MMP-9 stock solution (recombinant from HEK 293 cells, SIGMA-ALDRICH, Germany) and 1 μ L substrate in DMSO, resulting in final concentrations of 1.25 nM MMP-9, 40 μ M substrate and 1% DMSO. The

fluorescence was measured at 30 °C ($\lambda_{em} = 280 \text{ nm}/\lambda_{ex} = 360 \text{ nm}$) for 10 min every 30 s. Fluorescence units (FU) were converted to concentrations by measuring a dilution series of Trp.

2.4. *Substrate Used for Multi-parametric Surface Plasmon Resonance (MP-SPR) Measurements*

The peptide surface for studying MMP-9 activity was developed on Au SPR chips purchased from CENIBRA GmbH (Bramsche, Germany). The sensor chip consists of approximately 50 nm Au fabricated on glass slides with a 2 nm chromium adhesive layer between Au and glass. The fresh chips were cleaned with acetone and isopropanol (5 min each in an ultrasonic bath), rinsed with DI water, dried with a nitrogen stream and finally treated with oxygen plasma (5 min, at 100% power) before the measurements. The used chips were regenerated by chemical treatment (treatment in detergent, acetone and isopropanol (5 min each in ultrasonic bath) and oxygen plasma (5 min, 100% power).

2.5. *Multi-parametric Surface Plasmon Resonance Spectroscopy (MP-SPR)*

The real-time surface modification of the SPR Au sensor chips with a combination of linker molecules and peptides and their subsequent interaction with MMP-9 was monitored using an MP-SPR device (MP-SPR Navi 210A VASA instrument from BioNavis Ltd, (Tampere, Finland)) in the Kretschmann configuration. The MP-SPR is equipped with a standard PEEK flow cell with two channels of 1 μL each and three laser sources of 670 nm, 785 nm and 980 nm wavelength. Both flow channels were measured in parallel with all three laser sources. All measurements were performed in angular scan mode at all three wavelengths. However, to compare the change in SPR signal due to different biomolecular interactions occurring on the sensor, we used the data obtained at the 670 nm wavelength. Moreover, to determine the surface layer thickness by fitting the SPR intensity curve ([described in section 3.3.1](#)), the data measured at all three wavelengths are used to obtain more accurate values. The instrument allows the adjustment of several parameters. These include flow rate, system and flow chamber temperature, injection times and volume. A run table is used to define the parameters, which helps to design the experiment. The autosampler then performs the time-controlled injection of the samples.

2.5.1. *Immobilization of Peptide on SPR Au chips and its Interaction with MMP-9*

The cleaned and pre-activated SPR Au chips were first coated with PEG-based linker molecule (Lipoic acid – PEG-Maleimide (LA-PEG-Mal), MW = 1 kDa). Linker molecules (450 μM) diluted in PBS were perfused into the SPR flow cell attached to the Au chip (20 min, 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$). The linker binds covalently to Au via thiol (SH) – Au interaction. After immobilization of the linker molecules, the surface was washed with running buffer PBS (10 min, 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$) and further coated with peptide (195 μM in PBS) by continuous infusion of the peptide solution containing 3% DMSO (20 min, 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$). The free end of the linker containing a maleimide moiety binds

covalently to the C-terminal cysteine residues of the peptides via a maleimide-thiol coupling. Unbound peptides were removed by washing with PBS (15 mins, 20 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$). Following, the peptide surface was exposed to various concentrations (9000–0.05 μM) of MMP-9 (20 min, 10 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$). The purified MMP-9 solution was prepared in PBS, whereas for spiked samples, MMP-9 was diluted in RPMI-1640. To remove MMP-9, the surface was finally washed with PBS (20 min, 40 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$). All measurements were carried out in a continuous flow system at 30 °C and pH = 7.4. The scheme of the biosensing strategy is shown in [Fig.S1 \(Fig.S1 in the supplementary information\)](#).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Peptide Selection

Fig. 3. Comparative study of SPR signal change upon exposure of target peptides (peptide I and peptide II) and control peptide to MMP-9 at 30 °C in 1X PBS (pH = 7.4). a) Scheme showing peptides (target and control) interaction with MMP-9, b) SPR peptide binding response (each 195 μ M) on Au coated with linker molecules (450 μ M). Peptide in a continuous flow was bound to linker/ Au surface (20 min, at 10 μ L/min) and washed with PBS (15 min, 20 μ L/min) to remove the unbound peptides. A variation in peptide binding is visible. c) MMP-9 injection on peptides (target and control) (20 mins, 10 μ L/min) and the subsequent washing step (20 min, 40 μ L/min) to remove MMP-9 and the cleaved peptide fragments. The decrease in SPR signals below zero baseline for target peptides indicates that the peptides are cleaved by MMP-9, whereas the signal for the control peptide is above zero baseline, indicating that it is not hydrolyzed by MMP-9. d) An overview of SPR signal change due to varying concentrations of MMP-9. For the control peptide only the highest concentration of MMP-9 (3 nM) was tested. e) Mean peptide binding response. N represents the number of data set. f) The normalized SPR response shows the concentration dependent activity of MMP-9.

Previous studies showed, that the structure, dimension, and the stability of peptides significantly influence the catalytic efficiency of MMP-9 activity (the effective reaction rate constant) (González-Fernández et al., 2016), and their hydrolytic rate and cleavage sites (Huang et al., 2013). Therefore, to select a suitable peptide for our sensor design, the activity of MMP-9 on two target peptides (peptide I and peptide II) of slightly different lengths and a control peptide were monitored (Fig. 3a). However, prior to this study, it was important to evaluate the non-specific interactions of MMP-9 with the free sites of the sensor surface which can contribute to false signals (Shoji et al., 2011). For this, different sensing surfaces were prepared according to the protocol described in section S10 of supplementary information. The maximum binding response (0.017 Deg) of MMP-9 was observed on bare Au surface, with least binding signal of MMP-9 with a shift of 0.002 Deg was resulted from its interaction with Au functionalized with a specific combination of linker and peptide (Fig.S10 in the supplementary information). This result confirmed that using a specific combination of PEG-based linker and peptides offers an ideal sensing platform for MMP-9 detection. Therefore, throughout this work we used such a particular combination of linker and peptide to study MMP-9 activity. Subsequently, to select the peptide for further study, the peptides were covalently bound to the surface to obtain a stable surface. The immobilized target peptides were first exposed to various concentrations of MMP-9 ranging from 0.05 pM to 9 nM and subsequently washed with PBS. For control measurements with a control peptide, only one concentration of MMP-9 (3 nM) was used. Finally, the SPR end response obtained after 20 min washing with PBS was analyzed and compared.

Fig. 3b shows the SPR binding response of the target and control peptides. A variation in their binding response is visible. Fig. 3c illustrates MMP-9 solution injected/flowed over the target and control peptides, respectively. The initial increase in the SPR response during MMP-9 injection is due to the combined effect of glycerol (resulting in bulk effect) and the interaction of MMP-9 present in the sample solution (Fig.S13 in the supplementary information). A negative shift in the SPR signal for the target peptides (-0.01 Deg for peptide I and -0.06 Deg for peptide II) upon their exposure to 1 nM MMP-9 is observed, whereas for the control peptide, the signal due to 3 nM MMP-9 lies above the zero baseline at 0.001 Deg. The decrease in the SPR signal for target peptides proves that the target peptides are cleaved and the cleaved peptide residues are removed from the surface. Further, a negligible positive shift of the SPR response for the control peptide indicates that the control peptide is not hydrolyzed by MMP-9. Fig.3d shows the comparison of concentration dependent responses of MMP-9 cleavage. However, with absolute SPR values, the sensor response on MMP-9 concentration is not clear. Since a variation in peptide binding signal was observed at each measurement (Fig. 3e), the absolute response was normalized using equation 1 (González-Fernández et al., 2016, 2018). The normalized data clearly shows the dependence of SPR response for the target peptides on MMP-9 concentration (Fig. 3f).

Furthermore, the sensor coated with peptide II shows the highest SPR signal change for all concentrations of MMP-9 as compared to peptide I (Fig. 3d & 3f). To illustrate, for 3 nM MMP-9, the signal for peptide I and peptide II is decreased by 8% and 34.2%, respectively (Fig.3f). Being almost similar in sequence with only difference in their size, the higher signal response obtained after peptide II interaction with MMP-9 confirms that sensor coated with peptide II is a more efficient MMP-9 substrate. One possible reason could be a slightly longer peptide II with two additional Gly amino acid residues may offer better peptide orientation and more ease to MMP-9 to recognize the cleavage site. González-Fernández et al. tested peptides of different configurations, sizes, and have shown that the analytical performance of the peptide-based sensing surface can be improved depending on peptide sizes and their configurations (González-Fernández et al., 2016; Nisiewicz et al., 2022). Due to its higher sensitivity, peptide II was selected for further measurements.

$$\text{Normalized SPR Response [\%]} = \frac{\text{MMP-9 Response [Deg]}}{\text{Peptide [Deg]}} \times 100 \% \quad (1)$$

3.2. Comparison of Sensor Performance in Buffer and Cell Culture Medium (RPMI-1640)

Fig. 4. Normalized SPR signal change for target peptide (peptide II) exposed to varying MMP-9 concentrations (0.05 pM–9 nM) at 30 °C in 1X PBS, pH = 7.4 (black data points). All data represents the mean and standard deviation (n = 3) of the normalized SPR response. The linear detection range in buffer lies between 5 pM–9 nM MMP-9. The sensor performance was also tested in cell culture medium (RPMI-1640) (data shown in open circles). Each data point represents three replicates measured at identical experimental conditions. The values of the mean of the blank measurements (sample solution without MMP-9) and their standard deviation in % obtained in buffer and RPMI are shown with a blue straight line. The calculated limit of detection (LOD) for the proposed sensor calculated in the linear detection range in buffer and RPMI are 0.34 pM and 0.56 pM, respectively.

In Fig.4, the calibration curve obtained for peptide II exposed to varying concentrations (0.05 pM–9 nM) of MMP-9 is shown. For each concentration, three measurements were performed ($n = 3$). Due to the peptide cleavage by MMP-9, a decrease in the SPR signal below zero baseline is observed for all concentrations of MMP-9. With an increasing MMP-9 concentration, a higher signal change is observed. Above 5 pM MMP-9, the SPR response shows linear response (Fig. 4). The linear detection range lies between 5 pM–9 nM. Below 5 pM, the MMP-9 activity seems to be independent of its concentration. Nevertheless, even for 0.05 pM MMP-9, a non-zero signal suppression by 18.4% is demonstrated. This suggests that our sensor is capable of quantifying MMP-9 above 5 pM, however, below 5 pM with response around 18%, the sensor could still be used for the qualitative study of MMP-9. As anticipated, exposing peptide II to buffer without MMP-9 (blank measurement, Fig.S11 in the supplementary information), a negligible binding response of 1.23 % is observed. The limit of detection (LOD) is calculated using the standard equation 2 given by (Shabani et al., 2020):

$$LOD = \text{mean of blank} + 3 \times \text{STD of the blank} \quad (2)$$

Using equation 2, the LOD is first calculated in units of SPR response ('Deg') which is then finally converted into molar concentration (Fig. S12 in supplementary information). The LOD for the proposed sensor in PBS is 0.34 pM. This detection limit is below the reported clinical detection range of a wide range of diseases including metabolic syndrome (0.64 nM in healthy subjects, with values approaching 1.21 nM in individuals with metabolic syndrome) (Hopps et al., 2013), breast cancer (compared to 0.23 nM in healthy controls, the MMP-9 level elevated to 0.72 nM in plasma samples from breast cancer patients (Alrehaili et al., 2020), and multiple sclerosis (mean value of 3.98 ± 1.71 nM in control samples, with mean of active MMP-9 level increased to 7.89 ± 4.06 nM and 6.45 ± 4.52 nM, in short and long disease durations, respectively) (Biela et al., 2015). This suggests that a peptide sensing platform integrated with MP-SPR could potentially be implemented in clinical applications.

To compare the sensor performance in complex media, peptide II was exposed to MMP-9 spiked in cell culture medium (RPMI-1640) containing 10 mM HEPES (Fig. 4). The concentration range for investigating the activity of spiked MMP-9 on peptide II was chosen within the linear detection range of the sensor in buffer. For blank measurement (Fig.S11 in the supplementary information), RPMI without MMP-9 was used. The SPR signal change shows linear dependency on spiked MMP-9 concentrations, whereas a small binding response by 1.34 % is seen for RPMI without MMP-9. The LOD of the sensor in RPMI calculated using equation 2 is 0.56 pM and is still much lower than the clinically relevant range. Compared to the signal alteration with purified MMP-9, the overall signal response obtained in RPMI is lower. To demonstrate, upon challenging peptide II with 3 nM MMP-9 in PBS, the signal is decreased by approximately 40% relative to the zero baseline (Fig.4). In addition, it is visible in Fig.4 that the

slope of the sensor in RPMI is less steep than that in buffer (Fig. S12 in the supplementary information).

This indicates that the sensor is more sensitive in buffer than in RPMI. This is expected and could be due to the fact that RPMI contains not only salts but also other components such as glucose, amino acids and vitamins that could interfere with the actual signal. Although the MMP-related signal decrease in cell culture medium is smaller than in buffer, the ability of the sensor to detect different concentrations of MMP-9 in cell culture medium confirms the potential of our sensor for determining the activity of MMP-9 under physiological conditions.

3.3. Kinetic Analysis of the Sensor

3.3.1. Determination of Layer Thickness and Surface Coverage of Peptide II

The unique property of MP-SPR to record the entire binding SPR intensity curve (Fig. 5a) and using three different wavelengths allows for the precise estimation of the thickness and changes in the refractive index of the sensing layer. The SPR peak minima position and the position of total internal reflection in the intensity spectrum are paramount parameters to look at while studying layer properties (Fig. 5a). For this, the software *MP-SPR NaviTM LayerSolver_1.4.0.8* is used. Based on Fresnel theory, the software is used to determine the thickness (d) and refractive index (n) of various molecular layers (Belkilani et al., 2022). The software first models the optical molecular layers in terms of applied thickness (d), refractive index (n), and the absorption coefficients (k) using three wavelength methods (670 nm, 785 nm, and 980 nm) simultaneously (Fig. 5b). Finally, the software uses the inbuilt algorithm to estimate values for d , n , and k of each layer by continuous numerical iteration (Granqvist et al., 2013; Kari et al., 2017). The initial values of n , d , and k for each layer needs to be provided according to the literature values. The model is then applied to fit the SPR intensity data obtained for each layer and for all given wavelengths (Bionavis.com). The detail of layer modeling is described in *MP-SPR NAVI SOFTWARE MANUAL V6.4. X*. First, the blank Au surface is analyzed, followed by the subsequent layers. The initial values of d and n for different layers that we used to establish the layer model are, Au: $d = 50$ nm, $n = 0.17530-0.26397$; linker: $d = 7$ nm, $n = 1.4$; peptide II: $d = 4$ nm, $n = 1.35-1.40$; peptide II after cleavage: $d = 2.5$ nm, $n = 1.35-1.40$; peptide I: $d = 3.2$ nm; $n = 1.35-1.40$; peptide I after cleavage : $d = 1.7$ nm; $n = 1.35-1.40$, medium (PBS): $d = 0$, $n = 1.331$. During fitting, d is kept as a dependent variable for three wavelengths, whereas ' n ' is set to be an independent variable. The estimated values of d and n are further used to study the surface coverage (Γ) of each layer using "De Feijter" equation 6:

$$\Gamma = \frac{(n - n_0) d}{\frac{dn}{dC}} \quad (6)$$

where, n and n_0 are the refractive indices of the layer and medium, respectively. C is the ligand concentration, and $\left(\frac{dn}{dC}\right)$ is the refractive index increment.

Fig. 5c & 5d shows the SPR intensity curves of the sensor obtained at 670 nm as an example. The fitting is performed at all three wavelengths. The thickness of peptide I and peptide II layers before contact with MMP-9 resulting from fitting are (3.01 ± 0.94) nm and (3.64 ± 0.16) nm, respectively, which are comparable to their effective thickness, 3.20 nm and 3.96 nm, respectively, calculated using ACD/ChemSketch (freeware) 2021.2.1. The peptide I and peptide II layer thicknesses were reduced to (1.69 ± 0.14) nm and (2.26 ± 0.10) nm, respectively, after contact with MMP-9. These values are in good agreement with the calculated thickness of peptide I (1.7 nm) and peptide II (2.5 nm) after hydrolysis by MMP-9. The mean surface coverage (Γ) of peptide I and peptide II are (4.67 ± 0.20) ng/mm² and (5.64 ± 0.25) ng/mm², respectively, each with a molecular density of approx. 3 molecules/nm². Γ is slightly higher than that reported in the literature (Chen et al., 2013), however, Γ depends on other parameters such as the type of the peptide, surface properties, and experimental conditions. Nevertheless, the estimation of peptide thicknesses within the literature range clearly indicates that MP-SPR is a powerful surface analysis tool. This unique property of MP-SPR is advantageous and can potentially be applied to study and differentiate surface modification from nano- to micrometer range.

Fig. 5. Layer Modelling using LayerSolver software to obtain layer thickness, and surface coverage. a) An example of the entire SPR intensity spectrum displaying two most important parameters, i.e., total internal reflection (TIR) and SPR peak minima positions. of Au surface functionalized with linker, and peptide II before and after its interaction with MMP-9. The shift in SPR peak from bare Au surface to Au functionalized with linker is clearly visible, however, the signal shift due to peptide II before and after its exposure to MMP-9 is small and hence the shift is not easily observable. b) An example showing the scheme of sensing layer model before and after peptide II cleavage with MMP-9. c) & d) Better view of intensity curves showing the shift in SPR peak minima obtained at 670 nm for blank Au (blue solid line), Au coated with linker (red solid line), and finally peptide II coupled to linker on Au and the corresponding fitted curves (black dashed lines). Each curve is fitted with a defined layer model to obtain information on layer thickness and the corresponding refractive indices. The experimental data and the fitted curves are in good agreement.

3.3.2. Study of the Decay Rate of Peptide II Surface due to MMP-9

To examine peptide II surface decay rate as a function of MMP-9 concentration, the dissociation curve of SPR sensogram obtained after washing the MMP-9 exposed surface for 200 s is fitted against time (Fig. 6a) using an exponential decay function given by equation 7.

$$y = A \exp\left(-\frac{x}{t}\right) + y_0 \quad (7)$$

where, the amplitude 'A' denotes the initial value before the surface starts decaying, 'y₀' is the offset, and ' $k_{decay} = \frac{1}{t}$ ' gives the surface decay rate in [s⁻¹].

Fig.6a displays the experimental data (solid line + symbol) and the respective fitted curve (dotted lines) for four concentrations of MMP-9 diluted in PBS as an example. Fig. 6b shows a summary of calculated ' k_{decay} ' as a function of MMP-9 concentration. In general, ' k_{decay} ' increases with increasing MMP-9 concentration. The higher value of ' k_{decay} ' indicates that the surface is decaying much faster. Except for 1 nM, a clear variation in surface decay rate is observed with respect to MMP-9 concentration. The observed decay rate (k_{decay}) is comparable to the results reported for other classes of proteases (Wangkam et al., 2009). To the best of our knowledge, we report here for the first time the dependence of peptide surface decay rate on MMP-9 concentration.

Fig. 6. Evaluation of the peptide II surface decay rate due to MMP-9 activity in PBS. a) Decay curve for four concentrations of MMP-9 (solid line + symbol) and the fitted curves (dashed line). b) Plot of decay rate (k_{decay}) obtained by fitting SPR data using equation 7. k_{decay} increases with increasing MMP-9 concentration which clearly suggests that the peptide II surface decays much faster at higher concentration of MMP-9.

3.4. Kinetics of MMP-9 Reaction

To study the reaction rate of MMP-9 with the peptide II surface, the SPR response obtained during the interactions of various concentrations of MMP-9 and peptide II is analyzed using a method that employs a combination of standard Langmuir adsorption kinetics and Michaelis-Menten concepts. This method has been reported to monitor SPR signal to estimate the kinetic parameters of an enzymatic reaction (Fang et al., 2005; Lee et al., 2005; Lee et al., 2006; Shoji et al., 2011). Considering a simple, non-interacting 1:1 reaction, the enzyme-substrate reaction is typically described by:

where S and E are the substrate bound to the surface and the enzyme concentration in bulk solution, respectively. At first, the enzyme binds to the substrate and forms the substrate-enzyme complex (SE). Subsequently, the catalytic reaction occurs converting the substrate into the reaction product (S^*) which is then released from the enzyme. For the reaction described herein, the product consists of two parts: one cleaved peptide fragment bound to the surface, the other fragment released into the flow cell. The constants, k_a and k_d , corresponds to Langmuir association and dissociation rate constants, respectively. k_{cat} is the rate of reaction for the substrate-enzyme complex. If θ_S, θ_{ES} , and θ_{S^*} denotes the relative surface coverages of the substrate, enzyme-substrate complex, and product formed, bound to the surface, respectively, then the enzymatic reaction rate is described by equations:

$$\theta_S + \theta_{ES} + \theta_{S^*} = 1 \quad (9)$$

$$\frac{d\theta_{ES}}{dt} = \frac{k_a[E](1 - \theta_{ES} - \theta_{S^*}) - (k_d + k_{cat})\theta_{ES}}{1 + \beta(1 - \theta_{ES} - \theta_{S^*})} \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{d\theta_{S^*}}{dt} = k_{cat}\theta_{ES} \quad (11)$$

The fractional surface coverage, θ_{S^*} , was obtained from the SPR response curve of MMP-9 - peptide II reaction following the method described by Shoji et al (Shoji et al., 2011). The calculated, θ_{S^*} was plotted against time t to evaluate the slope equivalent to $k_{cat}\theta_{ES}$ within a definite time range. Moreover, the fractional surface coverage of enzyme on the unreacted sites is given by:

$$\lambda_{ES} = \frac{\theta_{ES}}{1 - \theta_{S^*}} \quad (12)$$

The value of λ_{ES} at time t was estimated using equation 12. According to the literatures, λ_{ES} increases to reach steady-state Langmuir-isotherm value when the reaction reaches equilibrium according to the quadratic equation given by:

$$\lambda_{ES} = \frac{-k_a E}{k_{cat}\lambda_{ES}} + \frac{k_a E + k_d + k_{cat}}{k_{cat}} \quad (13)$$

Since λ_{ES} depends on the enzyme concentration, E , in solution, equation 13 can be rewritten as:

$$E = \frac{k_{cat}\lambda_{ES}(k_{cat}\lambda_{ES} - k_d - k_{cat})}{k_a (k_{cat}\lambda_{ES} - k_{cat})} \quad (14)$$

Finally, equation 14 is used to calculate k_a , k_d , and k_{cat} of MMP-9 by fitting a plot of E against $k_{cat}\lambda_{ES}$.

For $k_{cat} \ll k_a, k_d$, the surface coverage of enzyme-substrate is assumed to be constant ($\frac{d\theta_{ES}}{dt} = 0$) (Lee et al., 2005). In this case, [equation 10](#) can be rewritten as:

$$\theta_{ES} = \frac{\theta_S E}{K_M} \quad (15)$$

where, the Michealis-Menten constant, K_M , is given by:

$$K_M = \frac{k_d + k_{cat}}{k_a} \quad (16)$$

Table 1. Comparison of kinetic analysis of MMP-9. k_a , k_d , and k_{cat} are obtained by fitting data shown in Fig.7 using equation 14.

Substrate Used	Assay Type	k_a [$M^{-1}s^{-1}$]	k_d [s^{-1}]	k_{cat} [s^{-1}]	K_M [M]	k_{cat}/K_M [$M^{-1}s^{-1}$]	Ref.
Collagen IV	*Heterogeneous	3.3×10^5	9.0×10^{-3}	9.0×10^{-3}	5.5×10^{-8}	1.63×10^5	(Shoji et al., 2011)
Collagen IV	*Homogeneous	-	-	-	1.0×10^{-5}	-	(Gioia et al., 2009)
Peptide	Heterogeneous	-	-	1.3×10^{-3}	5.5×10^{-8}	2.4×10^4	(Shin et al., 2013)
Peptide II	Heterogeneous	1.8×10^4	1.9×10^{-3}	5.5×10^{-4}	1.3×10^{-7}	4.1×10^3	This work
Peptide III	Homogeneous	-	-	2.3×10^{-1}	7.8×10^{-6}	5.5×10^6	This work

*Homogeneous assay – solution based assay; *Heterogeneous – surface based assays

[Table 1](#) presents the kinetic data of MMP-9 evaluated from [Fig. 7](#). To estimate the kinetic parameters, the data for four concentrations of MMP-9 in buffer (0.005 nM–9 nM) obtained in SPR measurements are used. OriginLab was used to fit the calculated data displayed in [Fig. 9](#) to [equation 14](#). The values of k_a , k_d , k_{cat} , K_M , and $\frac{k_{cat}}{K_M}$ obtained in our work from surface based assay (heterogeneous assay type) using SPR data and k_{cat} , K_M , and $\frac{k_{cat}}{K_M}$ derived from solution based assay (homogenous assay type) using FRET data are presented in [Table 1](#). The values obtained are close to the values reported in [Table 1](#). Shin et al. (Shin et al., 2013). have used MMP-9 substrate similar to peptide II with MMP-9 cleavage site located between Gly and Met amino acid residues. We observe a difference in K_M values depending on the assay type (homogeneous and heterogeneous) by almost two orders of magnitude. This could be due to differences in assay mechanisms or conditions inherent to each assay type that may have influenced the MMP-9 behavior. Shoji et al. (Shoji et al., 2011) have used collagen IV as the MMP-9 substrate on their surface-based MMP-9 assay, whereas Gioia and their group (Gioia et al., 2009) have investigated MMP-9 activity on collagen IV using solution-based assay. When

comparing their data for collagen IV substrate, the K_M values of MMP-9 in surface-based assay and solution-based assay differ by three orders of magnitude, suggesting that such variation is expected relative to the assay type. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that the kinetic parameters of MMP-9 are reported using peptide-based SPR data.

Fig. 7. Plot of MMP-9 bulk concentration and the calculated $k_{cat} \lambda_{ES}$. The data is fitted using equation 14 to estimate k_a , k_d , and k_{cat} . The values of k_a , k_d , and k_{cat} are further used to determine K_M (Table 1).

4. Conclusion

Table 2. Comparison of performances of peptide-based MMP-9 biosensors using different detection techniques. NA: Not available; CV & SWV: Cyclic & Square wave voltammetry; DPV: Differential Pulse Voltammetry; EIS: Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy; QCM: Quartz Crystal Microbalance; Si: Silicon; FET: Field-effect Transistor.

Detection Technique	LOD in Buffer	Linear Detection Range in Buffer	Sample Solutions	Real-time Detection	Peptide Tagged with	Performance of Kinetic Analysis	Study of Surface Properties	Ref.
Si nanowire FET	300 nM	NA	Buffer	yes	Streptavidin-Biotin	No	No	(Lee et al., 2009)
SWV	60 pM	60 pM – 50 nM	Buffer, Serum, and RPMI	yes	Methylene Blue	Yes	No	(Shin et al., 2013)
EIS	0.18 nM	0.6 nM - 4.87 nM	Buffer	yes	None	Yes	No	(Biela et al., 2015)
CV	7 pM	1 pM - 1 nM	Buffer	No	Methylene Blue	No	No	(Lee et al., 2017)
FRET	NA	NA	Buffer, wound exudates	No	Dabcyl, FITC	No	No	(Kang et al., 2019)
QCM-D DPV	QCM-D: 0.85 pM DPV: 0.45 fM	QCM-D: 0.24 pM – 0.06 μM DPV: 0.02 pM – 0.06 μM	Buffer and MMP-9 spiked in rat plasma samples	yes	Ferrocene	No	No	Nisiewicz MK et al., 2022
DPV	0.89 nM	0.6 nM – 12.19 nM	Buffer, cell secretion in DMEM	No	Ferrocene	No	No	Wang et al., 2024a
SPR	0.34 pM	5 pM – 9 nM	Buffer, RPMI-1640	yes	None	yes	yes	Our work

In this work, we presented for the first time a novel multi-parametric surface plasmon resonance (MP-SPR) biosensor based on short synthetic peptides to study MMP-9, a potential biomarker involved in the activation of various diseases, including cancer, Alzheimer's disease and multiple sclerosis. The SPR signal was monitored in a real-time, label-free and non-invasive manner. To demonstrate the ability of the sensor to discriminate the concentration-dependent activity of MMP-9, the gold surface of the SPR chips was first coated with a specific combination of linker and MMP-9-specific custom peptide and then exposed to various concentrations of MMP-9 diluted in buffer (PBS) and MMP-9 spiked in cell culture medium (RPMI-1640). A decrease in SPR signal relative to the zero baseline was observed, consistent with the expected peptide cleavage due to MMP-9 activity. The signal change showed a clear dependence on MMP-9 concentration between 5 pM - 9 nM in buffer, which covers the clinically relevant range. The estimated limit of detection in buffer and cell culture medium (RPMI) is 0.34 pM and 0.56 pM, respectively. The sensor performance was also compared with other peptide-based MMP-9 detection methods (Table 2). The present work is the first to report an SPR-based biosensor for MMP-9 detection. The detection limit is among the lowest reported for any detection technique. In contrast to previous work, no additional labels or signal-enhancing tags were used, which means that further optimization of the peptide sequence for SPR detection may further improve sensor performance. Furthermore, by taking advantage of the unique property of MP-SPR, we were able not only to demonstrate the concentration-dependent activity of MMP-9, but also to investigate surface layer properties such as the thickness of the sensing layer before and after cleavage and the corresponding surface coverage. The results are consistent with theoretical predictions of the peptide properties and provide valuable information that is critical to achieving better sensor performance. By carefully understanding and optimizing these surface properties, researchers can design a robust biosensor with higher sensitivity. These properties have not been reported in other studies (Table 2). In contrast to established ELISA kits, the SPR approach presented here provides data in real time, allowing kinetic analysis and more insight into the peptide-enzyme interaction (Table 1). Furthermore, the ability of the sensor to discriminate between different concentrations of MMP-9 spiked into cell culture medium shows that the sensor can be applied in the future to study MMP-9 released from cells under physiological conditions. Finally, the sensing principle is not limited to MMP-9 and can be applied to other proteases in the future by changing the peptide sequence.

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